

ORGANIZATIONAL BUSINESS STRATEGY: A CASE STUDY OF PHHP MARKETING IN MALAYSIA

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ABSTRACT

Strategic planning is the process of managing the organizational resources to meet its objectives, with taking the changing market opportunities into account. PHHP Marketing is one of the leading Phyto Fibre manufacturers in Malaysia. Its vision is “To become the market leader with innovation, added creativity and together with empowerment”, and its mission is “To offer the customers with the best product in a more innovative way than the rivals”. The main objectives are profitability and productivity, employee relation and retention, growth, marketing and customer relations. It uses few planning techniques, which would help organization to plan for strategic decisions. Few methods used such as Mintzberg’s Modes, SWOT analysis, BCG growth-share matrix, and value chain analysis. The environmental scanning is carried out to identify certain important factors that are essential in future. PESTEL analysis is done to brief on political, economic, social, technological, environmental, and legal factors. The important role played by stakeholders is identified as the group of people who are interested or affected by the decisions taken by the organization. PHHP Marketing is deciding to move into new market and create new market segments. Each functions in organization must has certain roles and responsibilities to face the challenging business environment. It might facing implementation problems when trying to obtain the necessary resources but with careful and effective planning, these strategy objectives could be achieved.

KEYWORDS: Business strategy, SWOT, PESTEL, BCG, Mintzberg’s Modes

INTRODUCTION

PHHP Marketing is one of the leading health food products - Phyto Fibre manufacturer in Malaysia. The group of companies is currently holding the 6th position in Malaysia in regard to the market share and the main aim of the company is to become the leading Phyto Fibre manufacturer within the next 2 years. It is clearly understood that the main objective of any organization would be to grow and expand after few years of operations. PHHP Marketing has identified some core competencies which has helped them to stand out from its competitors. This report explains the corporate vision, mission, objectives, policies, and the core competencies of PHHP Marketing, the problems they might face while planning strategic direction due to the changing economic

condition. The report also shows the number of different planning techniques that an organization could use and it shows how PHHP Marketing have effectively use of Mintzberg's Modes, SWOT analysis, BCG growth-share matrix and value chain analysis. The importance of carrying out a PESTEL analysis is given and also the value of stakeholders and the importance of stakeholder analysis are given out effectively. This report also shows that PHHP Marketing could use a number of methods as growth strategies and they have decided to move into a new market. It is also understood that all the divisions have certain roles and responsibilities in helping PHHP Marketing to achieve its objectives.

Strategic Management

Strategic management is the ongoing process of PHHP Marketing uses to form a vision, analyse its external environment and internal environment, and select one or more strategies to use to create value for customers and other stakeholders (Thompson & Martin, 2010).

Product Life Cycle

PHHP Marketing's new products progress through a sequence of stages from introduction to growth, maturity, and decline. This sequence is known as the product life cycle and it is associated with changes in the marketing situation (Stark, 2015), thus impacting the PHHP Marketing's marketing strategy and the marketing mix.

The product revenue and profits are plotted as a function of the life-cycle stages as shown in the graph below.

Figure 1: Product Life Cycle Stages

Introduction Stage

PHHP Marketing is seeking to build product awareness and develop their market for the product. There are few impacts on the marketing mix as follows:

- Product branding and quality level is established, and intellectual property defence such as patents and trademarks are obtained for Phyto Fibre which is the most sellable product.
- Pricing of product may be low to increase market share rapidly in short period.

- Distribution is monitored until consumers show acceptance of the product.
- Promotion is seeking to build product awareness and consumers product learning.

Growth Stage

PHHP Marketing is seeking to build brand preference while increase market share.

- Product quality is maintained, value-add features and customer support services are established.
- Pricing is maintained and enjoys increasing in product demand with minimal competition.
- Distribution channels are well established, and customers accept the product.
- Promotion strategies are rapidly used to aim for large group of customers.

Maturity Stage

A strong growth in sales will be weaken at maturity stage. There is arising in competition with similar product. The key objective at this stage is to protect market share while capitalize on profits.

- Product features are enhanced to differentiate the product from its competitors.
- Pricing is low to compete in competitive market.
- Distribution becomes more intensive and encourage preference over competing products.
- Promotion is rapidly change for product diversity.

Decline Stage

PHHP Marketing is having few options in decline stage.

- Finding new customers, new design and features.
- Reduce costs and maintain the product for a loyal niche segment.
- Promotion and continue to offer product and maintain at certain level of market share.

CORPORATE STRATEGIC PLAN

Corporate Vision Statement

The vision is intended to inspire PHHP Marketing’s employees to understand or “picture” the future ambitions of what the organization can become and to help begin a framework (Hoskisson, Hitt, & Ireland, 2009). The vision statement of PHHP Marketing is given below:

“To become the market leader with innovation, added creativity and together with empowerment”

Corporate Mission Statement

The mission statement defines the organization’s core intending to and the business or businesses in which it intends to work. This will explain the reason of existence of the organization and what it does, who it does for and how it does. The mission statement will help the stakeholders to have an idea on what organization hopes to do and its overall intension (Hoskisson, Hitt, & Ireland, 2009). The mission statement of PHHP Marketing is given below:

“To offer the customers with the best product in a more innovative way than the rivals”

Corporate Objectives

It is important that organization that exists is having its own objectives. It is essential to identify its own objectives and the purpose of why they are going to carry out operations (Hoskisson, Hitt, & Ireland, 2009). The objectives of PHHP Marketing are given below:

- Profitability and productivity – the ultimate objective of any business is to obtain profits and to increase its productivity over time. Profit maximizing becomes one of the most important objectives for PPHP Marketing and they aim to obtain 25% increment of profits within the next 2 years. The management should take necessary actions to increase the labour productivity by providing them with more and better training, a better and happy environment to work and all the necessary resources to achieve their targets (Spender, 2015).
- Employee relation and retention – one theory adopted at PPHP Marketing is that more the employees are kept happy and motivated, the easier for the organization to achieve its objectives. Both the vision and mission states about empowerment and the organization have been empowering its employees (Strickland, Gamble, & Thompson, 2001). PPHP Marketing is needs to build up a good relationship between the management and the employees and to retain them.
- Growth – the organization is planning to expand its operation in the coming two years. Few plans have been laid down and the decision needs to be implemented properly. The management is planning to set up new manufacturing plant and also planning to introduce new products.
- Marketing and customer relations – one main objective of PPHP Marketing is to market their products by giving an important message to its customers. Marketing is about understanding consumer buying trends, being able to get ahead product distribution needs and developing business partnerships that help organization to improve market share (Williams, 2002).

Mintzberg’s Modes

According to Henry Mintzberg, the organization's structure begins from the interaction of the organization's strategy, the environmental forces it experiences, and the organizational structure itself. When these come together, the organizations can perform well. In reverse, then the organization is likely to experience severe problems (Thompson & Martin, 2010). Different structures arise from the different characteristics of these organizations, and from the different forces that shape them. By understanding the organizational types that Mintzberg defines, PPHP Marketing can think about whether its structure is well suited to its conditions. If it isn't, it must think about what is needed to change things.

Figure 2: Mintzberg’s Modes of Strategic Decision Making

Entrepreneurial Mode

In entrepreneurial mode, PPHP Marketing's strategic planning is done by its Chief Executive Officer (CEO) or Top Management. He takes the full responsibility of business planning, focus and creates business opportunities. He has entrepreneurial skills. That is, he is good in planning, organizing, motivating people by having strong vision of direction for the growth of organization. He is a strong and bold leader.

Adaptive Mode

In adaptive mode, the CEO is changing his plans according to the changes in the business environment. He first makes a big plan, then he breaks it into smaller plans. This is done to adjust with the dynamic business environment. Then, he is combining all these plans to make a strategic business plan. In this method, the CEO works in a disorganized business environment with the objective to get the best business plan for PPHP Marketing.

Planning Mode

In planning mode, the Top Management makes the plan after analyzing the objectives and resources of PPHP Marketing. It is carefully considering all the factors before making the plan. In this method, its approach is very rational and gives prime importance to management processes in order to get logical business plan.

Logical Incrementalism

In this mode, Top Management has a rationally ideas of the business's mission and objectives. In its business strategies, it selects to use a collaborative process in which the organization probes the future and learns from some commitments rather than over comprehensive constructions of total strategies in PPHP Marketing. Thus, although the mission and objectives are set, the strategy can emerge out of argument, debate, and experimentation by business operations. This approach appears to be useful when the business environment is moving fast and when it is important to compromise and develop needed resources before obligating an entire corporation to a specific strategy (Thompson & Martin, 2010).

INTERNAL FACTOR ANALYSIS

This internal factor must be first understood before one goes about understanding the external factor in PPHP Marketing. When internal factor is understood, the points that emerge include its strengths, weaknesses, resources needed and competencies that must be built. An understanding of a firm's resources is a prerequisite to formulation of business strategy.

Internal factor analysis is usually done around traditional functions: production, marketing, finance, human resources, technology and so on. Each of these functions is further broken down to identify critical sub-functions, and their strength is also determined in terms of their contribution to organizational goals (Pahl & Richter, 2007).

Corporate Value Chain Analysis

It is a common fact that the businesses add value to their products at each stage of production. The production or the manufacturing process is divided into various segments and at each stage a certain value should be added to the products. For example, when the raw materials are transported for manufacturing, a value is added during packaging process and when the final product is

transported, another value is added (Ensign, 2001). This is where the value chain developed by Michael Porter comes into picture. A value chain is a set of activities that an organization carries out to create value for its customers. Porter proposed a general-purpose value chain that companies can use to examine all their organization activities and examine how they have connected each other (Ensign, 2001). It helps PHHP Marketing to understand the sources of value in an organization.

The following diagram clearly explains how a value chain would look like.

SOURCE: *Competitive Advantage: Creating and Sustaining Superior Performance* by Michael Porter. Copyright © 1985, 1988 by Michael E. Porter. All rights reserved.

Figure 3: Michael Porter's Value Chain Model

Primary Activities

Primary activities are directly involved in the conversion process of basic raw materials into final products including the receipt of raw materials from suppliers and marketing of products to customers. They are grouped into two types of activities related to product and market. Product related activities are the inbound logistics and operations, performed by the organization to add value to the product and services itself. Market related activities are outbound logistics, marketing and sales and services, performed by the organization to transfer the finished product or services to the customers (Porter, 1998).

Inbound Logistics

These include receiving the raw materials required for the PHHP Marketing's health food products making process, stacking and reclaiming the materials, and distribution of materials to production departments. Warehousing activities and supports are vital to product quality, balancing supply and demand, and create value-add to products and customers. Inbound Logistics activities can be included to primary activities (Dawar, 2013).

Operations Management

These include raw material handling and processing which involving receiving and handling of major raw materials like plant fibre including oat, roselle, psyllium husk and hawthorn berries. Raw materials are carefully examined to ensure its high-quality supplies. Manufacturing of products must meet the plant requirements, carrying out the major repairs of equipment in plant units, maintenance of equipment; repair of machineries and electronics equipment etc. Planning and monitoring of production also a vital activity (Dawar, 2013). Operation Management activities can be included to primary activities of PHHP Marketing.

Outbound Logistics

These include planning and despatch of products, distribution management intra and inter plants, transportation monitoring and control, warehousing and space availability, and customer order fulfilment by PHHP Marketing. Outbound Logistics activities can be included to primary activities.

Marketing and Sales

These include product management, price management, order placement management, product promotion management, product sales planning and control, planning and despatch, pricing and policy, customer contracts and relations management etc. Marketing and Sales activities can be included to primary activities of PHHP Marketing.

Service After Sales

PHHP Marketing provides services such as product warranty, commercial terms, quality aspects, delivery aspects, post sales contact handling, and customer complaint settlement procedure. Service after sales activities can be included to primary activities.

Support Activities

Material Management

These include identifying sources for various materials, selection of suppliers, taking requests from plant units, procurement of raw materials, components and parts, machinery and spares, consumables, stationery, servicing, transport contract management, discrepancy receipt, inventory control, and ensure the continuity supply of materials for production in PHHP Marketing.

Technology Development

PHHP Marketing is investing in bringing in modern technology to support and improve its operation which include quality assurance, engineering, production processes, and logistics operations. Key focus is toward processes automation to increase output and improve efficiency. The activities involved in improving the technology and the process used in the manufacture of products and their improvement, and the service procedures constitute Technology Development. Redesigning of processes, basic research, new product development process, use of information technology in service and distribution and the like are the different forms of technology development. Technology, a source of value, affords the competitive edge; a constant and successful pursuit of acquiring or developing technology differentiates a star performer from its rivals (Williams, 2002).

Human Resource Management

These include corporate coordination in manpower planning, recruitment, executive establishment, rules and policies, and welfare. The activities in human resources such as human resource development, management services such as quality circles, suggestion schemes, awards, and incentive schemes. Other activities such as corporate social responsibility, medical support, general administration, training and development (T&D), and HR information systems (Kotter, 2014).

Finance Management

These include treasury management, budgeting, costing, corporate accounts, raw material accounts, sales finance, operations & general accounts and works accounts, insurance, pay sections, stores accounts, purchase bills, project accounts, internal audit and stock verification.

Synthesis of Internal Factors – IFAS

Internal Factor Analysis Summary (IFAS) is to evaluate the worth of each identified strength to determine which strength is more critical than others. This tool furnishes both an enumeration of strengths and weaknesses in the functional areas of PHHP Marketing, and the value of each of them, thus the weighted score of strengths and weaknesses is calculated. This can be compared with those of the rival firms or industry standard. This tool also facilitates the understanding of the relationship among functional areas, and the degree of such relationship (Wheelen & Hunger, 2015). More specifically, a thorough understanding of the factors included in the IFAS is highly important to identified correct resources for PHHP Marketing.

Table 1: Internal Factor Analysis Summary (IFAS Table)

Internal Factors	Weight	Rating	Weighted Score	Comments
Strengths				
Competent and experienced staff	0.25	4.2	1.05	Strong in strategic planning
Innovative ideas	0.20	3.6	0.72	Competitive advantage
High products quality	0.15	3.0	0.45	Recognized and stand out
High capacity production facility	0.10	2.5	0.25	Capable of reducing production cost
Weaknesses				
Marketing expertise	0.15	3.8	0.57	Weak marketing and business development function
Raw materials from oversea	0.05	1.8	0.09	Dependence and subject to exchange rate fluctuations
Lack of an effective middle management	0.10	4.1	0.41	New recruitment and training policy
Total Scores	<u>1.00</u>		<u>3.54</u>	

Notes:

1. Each factor is weighted from 1.0 (most important) to 0.0 (not important). The total weights are sum to 1.00.

2. Each factor is rated from 5.0 (outstanding) to 1.0 (poor), based on the company's response to that factor.
3. Multiply each factor's weight and its rating to obtain each factor's weighted score.
4. Add up all the weighted scores usually works out between 1 (at its low) and 4 (at its highest). A score of less than 3.0 indicates a weak internal organization whereas that above 3.0 represents a stronger one.

The sum of the IFAS weighted scores of PPHP Marketing works out to 3.54 which is above the average of 3.0. It can be inferred that its internal factors are strong enough.

EXTERNAL FACTOR ANALYSIS

External factor analysis is a strategic management tool which allows the management of organization to examine the cultural, social, economic, demographic, political, legal, and competitive information. It indicates whether the organization can effectively take advantage of existing opportunities along with minimizing the external threats (Wheelen & Hunger, 2015). Similarly, it will help PPHP Marketing to formulate new strategies and policies based on existing position of the organization.

PESTEL Analysis

It is a common fact that the organization carry out external environmental audit to identify their strengths and capabilities within the organization and to have an understanding about what is happening in the outside world. External environmental audit or scanning a PESTEL analysis could be carried out by detecting early signs of opportunities and threats that may influence its current and plans. There are six factors in PESTEL analysis which stand for Political, Economic, Social, Technological, Environmental and Legal (Porter, 1998).

Figure 4: PESTEL Analysis Factors

Political

Political factors play a huge role for an organization and it influence on its decisions. It might place obligations and duties on an organization. Some factors are tax policies, safety regulations issued by government and international regulations. PPHP Marketing must produce products per given standards and adhere to trade agreements, tariffs or restrictions.

Economic

The market condition or the economy of the country is bound to change from time to time. The economy might be in a boom, in a recession or in a growing inflation problem. These can influence an organization and it will change the plans set up by PPHP Marketing. They must cope up anything because depending on the economic condition, they might not get to market their products well and sales may not increase. It is clearly understood that if an economy is in a recession, then it will have high unemployment levels, low spending power and lower stakeholder confidence.

Social

This mainly considers people's lifestyles and behaviour. Different people have different choices and their taste and preferences differ. PPHP Marketing should always try to produce a product and market it effectively which can capture a wider customer range. Factors such as mood and demographics should be considered. The company should always consider the population changes in the country. Changes in the structure of a population will affect the demand and supply of goods and services. PPHP Marketing must produce products that will suit to different segments in the market.

Technological

An organization use modern technology to manufacture products and market their products. By moving on technology, it exchange of information faster and help the business to react quickly to changes. To be more competitive in the market, PPHP Marketing use machineries in modern technology to produce its products and use modern techniques in production of products. With modern technology in production, PPHP Marketing can increase its output and produce high quality products which able to compete in the competitive market.

Environmental

Organization should always pay high concern to the environment impact. Products should be produced, that will minimize the environment pollution. To keep the environment clean, it should comply with government's policies and legislations. Other factors such as floods, should be considered as it will disrupt production and supply operations.

Legal

Organization should always adhere to certain rules and regulations which are set up by government. Labour laws is important and must consider to ensure the effectiveness of human resource management. It is also important to produce products per certain standards and implemented legally.

Synthesis of External Factors – EFAS

Table 2: External Factor Analysis Summary (EFAS Table)

External Factors	Weight	Rating	Weighted Score	Comments
Opportunities				
Expansion into regional markets	0.25	4.0	1.00	Increase sales volume and improve market share
Technological advancements	0.20	3.0	0.60	High output and efficient production
Strategic partnership with vendors	0.10	2.5	0.25	A reduction in raw materials price and lead time
Threats				
High competition	0.25	4.0	1.00	Increasing in new competitors
Changes in customer demands and preferences	0.10	3.2	0.32	Service comparative and high customization
Government policies and legislations	0.10	3.0	0.30	Impact on foreign workers' costs and GST
Total Scores	<u>1.00</u>		<u>3.47</u>	

Notes:

1. Each factor is weighted from 1.0 (most important) to 0.0 (not important). The total weights are sum to 1.00.
2. Each factor is rated from 5.0 (outstanding) to 1.0 (poor), based on the company's response to that factor.
3. Multiply each factor's weight and its rating to obtain each factor's weighted score.
4. Add up all the weighted scores usually works out between 1 (at its low) and 4 (at its highest). A score of less than 3.0 indicates a weak internal organization whereas that above 3.0 represents a stronger one.

The sum of the EFAS weighted scores of PPHP Marketing works out to 3.47 which is above the average of 3.0. It can be inferred that the organization is taking advantage of existing opportunities along with minimizing the potential adverse effects of external threats.

CORPORATE STRATEGY FORMULATION

Strategy formulation is a continuing process to develop and review forthcoming strategies that allow PPHP Marketing to achieve its objectives, seeing its competences, limitations, and the environment in its operation. In the strategy formulation process, produces a clear set of recommendations, with supportive reasoning, that review as essential the mission and objectives of the organization, and supply the strategies for realising them (Lehmann, 2012). Thus, PPHP Marketing is trying to adjust the current objectives and strategies in the ways to make the organization more effective.

Directional Strategy

PPHP Marketing's vision and mission are the most fundamental forms of directional strategy. A mission statement defines its business purpose and sets the overall tone for business strategic

direction. A vision statement outlines what they hope to achieve as work toward its mission and helps to focus on strategy toward reaching specific business goals (Hoskisson, Hitt, & Ireland, 2009).

Figure 5: Corporate Directional Strategies

Growth Strategies

PHHP Marketing's growth strategies can be classified into two categories:

- Concentration within existing industry: vertical and horizontal growth
- Diversification into other lines of business or industries: concentric and conglomerate

Vertical Growth

The strategy taken by PHHP Marketing is taking over functions earlier in the value chain that were previously provided by suppliers. Some outsourced processes are returned to internal production that have advantages like in cost, stability and quality of products, that making operations more difficult for competitors.

Horizontal Growth

PHHP Marketing is involving in expanding existing products into East Malaysia to extend its market segments. The product range is increasing to support new market segments with different demand and needs.

Concentric Diversification

PHHP Marketing is venture into packaging production which is having synergy with the organization's existing lines of business. It is creating a situation to gain special advantages from commonalities such as technology, customers, distribution, and location.

Conglomerate Diversification

There are no strategy alternatives for PHHP Marketing for growth involves diversifying into a line of business unrelated to the current ones.

Stability Strategies

There are several circumstances in which the most appropriate growth stance for a company stability is, rather than growth. Three alternatives as below, in which the actual strategy actions are similar, but differing primarily in the circumstances motivating the choice of a stability strategy and in the intentions for future strategic actions (Strickland, Gamble, & Thompson, 2001).

Pause and Then Proceed

PHHP Marketing is wait and look at the market conditions before launching the full-fledged grand strategy. Also, the organization that has intensely followed the expansion strategy would wait till the time the new strategies seeps down the organizational levels and look at the changes in the organizational structure before taking the next step.

No Change

There are certain market segments in low sales that may require to remain as to compete with few competitors. This is happening in few small towns in West Malaysia.

Grab Profits

PHHP Marketing is aiming to maintain the business profit by whatever means possible. When the profitability is low, it may cut costs, reduce investments, raise prices, increase productivity or adopt any methods to overcome the temporary difficulties. The profit strategy can be followed when the problems are temporary or short-lived and will go away with time.

Retrenchment Strategies

The retrenchment strategy is adopted when PHHP Marketing is aim at reducing its business operations with the view to cut expenses and reach to a more stable financial position.

Turnaround

The need for a turnaround strategy arises because of the changes in the external environment, change in the government policies, saturated demand for the product, a threat from the substitute products, changes in the tastes and preferences of the customers, etc (Kaplan & Norton, 2001). In 2006, PHHP Marketing announced the cost-cutting measures by downsizing its production facility and capacity, but unfortunately, it suffered huge losses in market share. Then in 2007, PHHP Marketing come back with centralized production and warehousing strategy. Today, it is one of the largest Phyto Fibre manufacturers in Malaysia.

Liquidation

The liquidation strategy is the most unpleasant strategy adopted by the organization that includes selling off its assets and the final closure or winding up of the business operations. It is the most crucial and the last resort to retrenchment since it involves serious consequences such as a sense of failure, loss of future opportunities, spoiled market image, loss of employment for employees, etc (Kaplan & Norton, 2001). PHHP Marketing is doing their very best to avoid such strategy become reality in its organization.

BCG Growth-Share Matrix

An organization is most likely to engage in the production of large number of products and it is the duty and the responsibility of PHHP Marketing to identify and decide which products should focus more on investment. Simply this means that the business needs to allocate its investment on each product to make things easier for the organization a BCG growth-share matrix could be prepared (Marren, 2007).

Figure 6: BCG Growth-Share Matrix

As shown in Figure 6, two key terms used in BCG growth-share matrix is ‘Market Growth’ and ‘Market Share’. Products in PPHP Marketing can be categorized as Stars, Question Marks, Cash Cows and Dogs. The number of products could be categorized into these four segments are:

- Stars – Phyto Fibre
- Question Marks – Phyto Aloe Vera, IG-Rich Colostrum
- Cash Cows – Phyto Greens, Ophira Collagen
- Dogs – Alijaga Coffee, Green Tea

The following diagram clearly shows the characteristics of BCG growth-share matrix in PPHP Marketing.

<p>STARS High market growth High market share Cash neutral</p>	<p>QUESTION MARKS High market growth Low market share Cash absorbing</p>
<p>CASH COWS Low market growth High market share Cash generating</p>	<p>DOGS Low market growth Low market share Cash neutral</p>

Figure 7: Characteristics of the Segments of BCG Growth-Share Matrix

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

It is important that the main motive of any organization is to achieve the goals and objectives which are set up before operations and to grow over time, but the question is whether this is always possible. Will PPHP Marketing end up in its desired place? Some strategy might work out, but some might decline.

Strategy Implementation Issues

Some strategies must be avoided or use with caution in organization. There are few concerns described as follows.

Follow the Leader

The Top Management decision making may be a good idea, but it must careful consider PPHP Marketing's strengths and weaknesses. Example the Indonesia market penetration within 3 months.

Hit Another Home Run

It is very expensive and massive cost should spend to develop another star product like Phyto Fibre. It might not successful in market and create losses to organization.

Arms Race

Certain market segments or products may have to aggressively compete with competitors to maintain or increase market share. Example Alijaga Coffee for Malay market. With the increase in advertising, promotion, R&D costs may reduce its revenue.

Do Everything

It is more competitive advantage to have more products in the market and increase market segments, but as time goes by, more and more resources are needed and exhausted. The focus shall on few strong ones.

Stakeholder Measures and Value Analysis

Stakeholders could be recognised as the group of people who are interested or affected by the decisions taken by PPHP Marketing. Stakeholder analysis is the review and consideration of the impact of stakeholders in businesses. This is becoming increasingly important as non-shareholder entities, including customers, employees, communities and business partners, have become more key to business success (Westland, 2017). PPHP Marketing need to understand the interest of each stakeholder and strategize on how to address them in business practices. Organization should understand that it is not all about generating sales and obtaining higher profits, they should also operate or take actions in the way that could or should satisfy many people, which keeping all the stakeholders satisfied at once and their needs (Marren, 2007). PPHP Marketing have identified many stakeholders who are interested or affected by their decisions. The following table shows possible stakeholders and their concerns.

Table 3: Stakeholder and Stakeholder Concerns

Stakeholder	Stakeholder Concerns
Shareholders	Return on investments, income and profits, strategic plans
Employees	Wages and salaries, job security, compensation, respect
Customers	Value-add, quality, customer care, ethical products
Suppliers	Business opportunities, fair and equitable treatment

Community	Jobs, environmental protection, truthful communication
Government	Taxation, GST, legislation, employment, truthful reporting, diversity, legalities, externalities

PHHP Marketing is prioritize the stakeholders into four parts as high influence low interest, high influence high interest, low influence low interest, and low influence high interest. The following diagram clearly shows the method of prioritize its stakeholders.

Figure 8: Prioritization of Stakeholders

The four groups of stakeholders identified by management of PHHP Marketing as follows:

- Keep satisfied – High influence and low interest
 - Government, major customers, and media
- Manage closely – High influence and high interest
 - Shareholders, existing and potential investors
- Apathetics – Monitor
 - Small customers, small shareholders
- Defenders – Keep informed
 - Employees, local community, suppliers

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